

PRETERM BIRTH

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Annotation Premature birth occurs for various reasons. Most preterm births happen spontaneously. Quality care before and during pregnancy and between pregnancies ensures a positive pregnancy experience for all women.

Key words: Premature birth, problems, infections, indication, risk, results.

Introduction

- An estimated 15 million babies are born prematurely each year (before the full 37 weeks of pregnancy), and this number is increasing.
- Complications from preterm birth are the leading cause of death for children under five years of age. So, in 2015 they led to approximately one million deaths.
- Three-quarters of these deaths could have been prevented with available cost-effective interventions, even in the absence of intensive care units.
- Preterm birth rates range from 5% to 18% of births in 184 countries.

Babies born alive before 37 completed weeks of gestation are considered preterm. Prematurely born children are divided into categories depending on the gestational age:

- children born extremely premature (less than 28 weeks);
- children born significantly premature (between 28 and 32 weeks);
- children born moderately and slightly premature (between 32 and 37 weeks).

In the absence of medical indications, induction of labor or a caesarean section should not be performed before 39 completed weeks of pregnancy.

Problem

An estimated 15 million babies are born too early each year. This is more than one in ten children. Approximately one million children die every year due to complications associated with preterm birth. 1 Many surviving children suffer from lifelong disabilities, including learning difficulties and visual and hearing problems.

Worldwide, preterm birth is the leading cause of death for children under the age of five. Preterm birth rates are on the rise in almost all countries with reliable data.

There are huge disparities in survival rates around the world. In low-income countries, half of babies born before 32 weeks of gestation (two months early) die for lack of feasible, cost-effective interventions such as warmth, breastfeeding support and essential health care in case of infections and breathing difficulties. In high-income countries, almost all such children survive. Suboptimal use of technology in middle-income settings increases the burden of disability among preterm infants who survive the neonatal period.

Decision

More than three-quarters of preterm infants can be saved through practical, cost-effective care, such as providing essential care during childbirth and the postpartum period to every mother and child, and antenatal steroid injections (pregnant women at risk of preterm onset, labor activity in order to strengthen the lungs of children), and the use of the kangaroo method (ensuring skin-to-skin contact between mother and baby and frequent breastfeeding), and antibiotic treatment of neonatal infections.

For example, continuity of obstetric care in settings where there are effective obstetric services can reduce preterm birth rates by about 24%.

Preventing death and complications from preterm birth starts with a healthy pregnancy. Quality care before and during pregnancy and between pregnancies ensures a positive pregnancy experience for all women. WHO guidelines for

antenatal care include key interventions to prevent preterm birth, such as counseling on healthy diets and optimal nutrition and on tobacco and drug use; measurement of the fetus, including with the help of ultrasound, to determine the gestational age and detect multiple pregnancies; and at least 8 contacts with healthcare professionals during pregnancy to identify and manage other risk factors such as infections. Improving access to contraceptives and empowerment can also lead to a reduction in preterm births.

Literature

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